

ICCM24 – 24TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON COMPOSITE MATERIALS
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Modeling and Control of Polymerization Exotherm of an Acrylic Thermoplastic Resin in the Pultrusion Process

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Context – INFRAlight Project

INFRAlight Project

Towards sustainable and digitalized mobility

Digitize and automate rail transport

Reduce costs and facilitate line operation and maintenance

Reduce the carbon footprint of transport

- Continuous fibre recyclable thermoplastic composite rails
- Rails manufacturing by reactive thermoplastic pultrusion

Alexander A. Safonov, Pierpaolo Carlone, Iskander Akhatov, 15 January 2018
doi : <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2017.09.093>

- Continuous fibre recyclable thermoplastic composite rails
- Rails manufacturing by reactive thermoplastic pultrusion

- High production rate, high efficiency.
- Low production costs.
- Ability to produce profiles of infinite length.

Experimental Thermal Study

IRT M2P unidirectional Glass/ELIUM

Experimental Thermal Study

Experimental Manufacturing of Pultruded Plates Glass/ELIUM

Micrographic characterization

**Pultruded 10 mm thick Plate Glass/ELIUM
IRT M2P – 110°C**

Overall Goal

- ✓ Optimize the process, to achieve a complete polymerization at the highest production speed
- ✓ Necessity of a fine and predictive model to support process control

Complex thermal behavior

- Strong thermo-kinetic coupling due to the complex polymerization of the Elium resin.
- Development of a numerical model of the pultrusion process by coupling heat transfer equations with the polymerization kinetics of the resin.
- Influence of Elium's specific kinetic behavior on the thermal regime during pultrusion.
- Evolution of material properties as a function of both temperature and degree of conversion.

The challenges of Pultrusion

Thermal expansion
 $\frac{\Delta v}{v}$

Cure Shrinkage
 $\frac{\Delta v}{v}$

Boundary condition :
 $\sigma_{max} = \sigma_{adhesion}$

Boundary conditions :
 $RTC, h_c \dots$

Boundary condition :
 $\phi ?$

S. Sourour, M.R. Kamal, January 1976
 doi : [https://doi.org/10.1016/0040-6031\(76\)80056-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0040-6031(76)80056-1)

Thermal Model & BC

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_t} = \frac{1-v_f}{\lambda_r} + \frac{v_f}{\lambda_f}$$

$$\lambda_t = v_f \lambda_f + (1 - v_f) \lambda_r$$

$$C_p = v_f C_{pf} + (1 - v_f) C_{pr}$$

$$\rho = v_f \rho_f + (1 - v_f) \rho_r$$

$$\rho C_p \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + v_x \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) + \nabla(-\lambda \nabla T) = \phi$$

Data sheet: polymeres-netzsch-com/pmma-polymethacrylate-de-methyle
 Data sheet: techniques-ingenieur/proprietes-des-fibres

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k_p \sqrt{\frac{2f(k_{d,P_1}[P_1] + k_{d,P_2}[P_2] + k_{d,P_3}[P_3])}{k_t}} (1 - \alpha)$$

Damien Gacon et al., Composite Materials hal -04696743 (Jul 2024)

- k_p : Radical polymerization rate constant
- k_{d,P_i} : Dissociation rate constant
- k_t : Termination rate constant
- f : Efficiency of the peroxide initiator
- $[P_i]$: Concentration of the peroxide initiator

Validation of the kinetic model using COMSOL

Assumptions:

- Thermal study under adiabatic conditions using COMSOL Multiphysics.

- Validation of the results obtained in COMSOL with the actual experimental data

Influence of the source term at 110°C

Conclusion

- A temperature rise due to the exothermic heat generated by polymerization.
- With a source term, the temperature exceeds the applied temperature

System setup in COMSOL

Conclusion

- Polymerization starts at the surface due to the high thermal conductivity of the die.
- Temperature and polymerization are delayed at the core.
- Homogeneous heat transfer.

System setup in COMSOL

Conclusion

- Polymerization starts at the surface due to the high thermal conductivity of the die.
- Temperature and polymerization are delayed at the core.

Surface analysis

Relevant thermo-kinetic coupling

- Allows to capture the thermal evolution
- But !!**
 - Slight shift in temperature at the surface !
 - Problem for the thick part such as Rail !
 - **Thermal contact resistance ?**

Core analysis

- A delay at the core is observed compared to experimental data
- **Can porosity affect thermal conductivity ?**

Thermal Optimization of TCR

Conclusion

- The surface thermal profile shows better agreement with the experimental one with TCR
- Proportional relationship between TCR and the polymerization rate

Evolution of TCR as a function of conversion degree

A linear relationship between shrinkage and alpha (*literature*)

$$\alpha_{moy} = \frac{\sum_i \alpha_i}{thickness}$$

- Relationship between TCR and chemical shrinkage ?
- Sudden increase in TCR due to material debonding ?? possible link with mechanical effects ?

Optimization of transverse thermal conductivity

Conclusion

- Thermal conductivity decreases along the die as the reaction progresses.
- Relation with porosity?
- The central thermal profile shows better agreement with experimental one.

Conclusion

- Implementation of thermo-kinetic coupling between the thermal behavior and the polymerization kinetics of the Elium resin.
- Comparison with experimental results shows a good phenomenological representation of exothermic effects and heat transfer.
- Representation of a possible effect of TCR and λ .

Perspectives

- **Consideration of additional physical phenomena** : TCR (α, T) as a function of chemical shrinkage, thermal conductivity as a function of porosity.
- **Development of a model**, that explains the presence of porosity at the core of the material by coupling physico-chemical phenomena with the mechanical behavior of the composite.
- Numerical thermal application in the case of the **pultruded rail**.

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Thank you !

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The longitudinal and transverse thermal conductivities (λ) are different :

$$[\lambda] = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_l & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_t & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda_t \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_l} = \frac{1-v_f}{\lambda_r} + \frac{v_f}{\lambda_f}$$

$$\lambda_t = v_f \lambda_f + (1 - v_f) \lambda_r$$

- $\lambda_r = 0.25$ [W/m*K] : Thermal conductivity of the resin
- $\lambda_f = 1$ [W/m*K] : Thermal conductivity of the fiber

$$C_P = v_f C_{Pf} + (1 - v_f) C_{Pr}$$

$$\rho = v_f \rho_f + (1 - v_f) \rho_r$$

- $C_{Pf} = 830$ [J/kg*K] : Specific heat capacity of the fiber
- $C_{Pr} = 1470$ [J/kg*K] : Specific heat capacity of the resin
- $\rho_r = 1195$ [kg/m³] : Density of the resin
- $\rho_f = 2550$ [kg/m³] : Density of the resin

Thermal properties	10 mm plate	4 mm plate
v_f	0.7	0.67
λ_l	0.775 [W/m*K]	0.76 [W/m*K]
λ_t	0.52632 [W/m*K]	0.5102 [W/m*K]
C_P	1034.8 [J/kg*K]	1022 [J/kg*K]
ρ	2136 [kg/m ³]	2116.4 [kg/m ³]

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Assumptions

- The die's length (L) is much greater than the composite thickness(e) : $L \gg e$
- Boundary conditions : $\alpha(\bar{x} = 0) = 0$ et $\bar{T}(\bar{x} = 0) = 0$
- Steady state; Homogeneous and isotropic material; Constant thermal properties

$$\rho C_p v_x \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} - \lambda \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} \right) - \Delta H_v v_x \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial x} = 0$$

\bar{T} et $\bar{\alpha}$ are the average temperature and degree of conversion

$$\frac{\partial^2 \bar{T}}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\rho C_p v_x}{\lambda} \frac{\partial \bar{T}}{\partial x} + \frac{\phi_0}{\lambda e} + \frac{\Delta H_v v_x}{\lambda} \frac{\partial \bar{\alpha}}{\partial x} = 0$$

Adimensionnalisation : $\bar{\theta} = \frac{\bar{T}}{T_a}$; $\bar{x} = \frac{x}{L}$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \bar{\theta}}{\partial \bar{x}^2} - \frac{\rho C_p v_x L}{\lambda} \frac{\partial \bar{\theta}}{\partial \bar{x}} + \frac{\phi_0 L^2}{\lambda e T_a} + \frac{\Delta H_v v_x L}{\lambda T_a} \frac{\partial \bar{\alpha}}{\partial \bar{x}} = 0$$

1D Thermal Analysis

$$P_e = \frac{\text{convection}}{\text{conduction}}$$

$$N_u = \frac{\text{Heat flux}}{\text{conduction}}$$

$$C = \frac{\text{Exothermic reaction}}{\text{conduction}}$$

$P_e \gg N_u, C \gg 1$

$N_u \gg P_e, C \gg 1$

$C \gg N_u, P_e \gg 1$

$P_e, N_u \gg C \gg 1$

$1 \gg P_e, C, N_u$

$P_e, C, N_u \gg 1$

